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Bridging the Generation Gap: Understanding Collaboration Challenges and Opportunities in Multigenerational Workplaces

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Abstract

This qualitative study employed a hermeneutic phenomenological approach study and explored how employees across generations perceived and experienced collaboration in the workplace. Five (5) participants were interviewed to understand their perspectives on generational stereotypes, communication challenges, and successful collaboration. Participants identified stereotypes regarding technology use, work ethic, and career commitment across generations. However, they also recognized the potential for collaboration and learning from each other's strengths. Linguistic barriers, communication style differences, and emotional responses were reported as hurdles to effective communication. The study highlighted the need for empathy, adaptability, and understanding to bridge these gaps. Participants reported positive experiences from working in diverse teams. Integrating new ideas, embracing change, and leveraging the expertise of each generation can lead to innovation, knowledge sharing, and organizational success.

Keywords: *generational collaboration, workplace diversity, communication barriers, multigenerational teams, qualitative research*

Introduction

The global workforce underwent a remarkable transformation, characterized by the presence of four distinct generations collaborating within the same professional landscape. While the diverse perspectives and experiences of each generation hold immense potential for innovation and growth, navigating communication gaps and differing work styles can be significant challenges to effective collaboration Danley, K. (2020). While research on multigenerational workforces has gained traction in recent years, there remain significant gaps in the understanding of collaboration specifically. Existing studies often focus on individual generation characteristics or broad organizational challenges, neglecting the nuanced dynamics of multigenerational teamwork Lackey, K. L. (2019). Additionally, much of the research relies on quantitative surveys or case studies, limiting the ability to capture the lived experiences and subjective perspectives of individuals working across generations. Driven by the belief that understanding these dynamics is crucial for organizations to optimize their workforce, foster productive collaboration, and leverage the unique strengths of each generation. By examining the interplay of generational differences in communication, technology use, work preferences, leadership styles, and hope to provide valuable insights that can inform strategies for building cohesive and high-performing teams Rajput, N., Bhatia, S. P., & Malhotra, B. (2019). Semi-structured interviews allowed this study to delve into specific challenges and opportunities related to collaboration, capturing the rich texture of individual narratives and perspectives. Through reflexive thematic analysis of the interview data, it identifies key themes and patterns that shed light on the complexities of multigenerational teamwork. By giving voice to the diverse experiences of employees, this study seeks to generate practical recommendations for fostering effective collaboration and unlocking the full potential of multigenerational workforces.

Research Questions

In today's workplaces and organizations, employees encounter difficulties but also face some benefits. The purpose of this qualitative research specifically through hermeneutic phenomenological approach was to explore the collaboration challenges and opportunities faced by employees in multigenerational workplaces. In the study collaboration challenges and opportunities are broadly defined as the perceived difficulties and potential benefits encountered when individuals from different generations work together on tasks or projects they work together. Specifically, this seeks to answer the following:

1. How do employees across generations perceive and describe the stereotypes associated with their own and other generations when it comes to collaboration?
2. What collaboration challenges do the employees experience within Multigenerational organizations?
3. How do employees across generations experience successful collaboration, and how does it benefit the organization?

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers used qualitative research design specifically through hermeneutic phenomenology. In-depth interview methodology to explore the lived experiences of employees in multigenerational workplaces and recruit participants from a variety of industries and organizations, ensuring a representative sample of the workforce. Brahmabhatt (2019) used a qualitative approach to explore the impact of generational diversity on the workplace. It found that while values and behaviors might be similar, priorities differ across generations.

Rajput et al. (2019) qualitative study that also used interviews to understand the challenges faced in managing a multigenerational workforce. It highlighted the need for HR managers to understand generational differences and create flexible work environments.

The design is fitted to this study because it focuses on understanding subjective experiences of collaboration that allows for in-depth exploration of communication styles and challenges, and captures the nuances of Multigenerational dynamics in the workplace. This qualitative design has some limitations. Findings are subjective and may not generalize. Participants' memory and communication can affect results. The design lacks quantitative data on collaboration effectiveness.

While this study primarily uses qualitative methods, future research could adopt mixed-method approaches to deepen the understanding of quantitative outcomes like team performance metrics in multigenerational setups.

Participants

The participants of the study were employees from four generations: Baby Boomers (born 1946-1964), Generation X (born 1965-1980), Millennials (born 1981-1996), and Generation Z (born 1997-2012).

The participants of this study had to meet the following criteria to be included in the sample: Should have worked in an organization with a multigenerational workforce (having at least employees from two or more of the target generations); should be employed for 1 year or more (for Gen Z) and 5 years or more (for Gen Y, Gen X, and Baby boomers); should be 22-65 years of age; and should be willing and able to participate in a semi-structured interview.

The study employed purposive sampling to recruit participants for the semi-structured interviews, Patton, M. Q. (2002) describe purposive sampling as a procedure where individuals who are most knowledgeable or experienced with the phenomenon of interest (in this case, collaboration in Multigenerational workplaces) are selected to become participants.

Instrument

The study used the triangulation method by Patton (1999) involving multiple methods or data sources to gain a comprehensive understanding of the research phenomena. The study conducted face-to-face interviews to facilitate insights by directly engaging with participants. The triangulation approach aims to enhance the depth and validity of the research findings.

Procedure

After recruiting participants, individual face-to face interviews were scheduled at their convenience. Informed consent was obtained, and the study's purpose, data collection, and participant rights were explained. With permission, interviews were audio-recorded using a semi-structured guide to explore collaboration experiences in multigenerational teams. Open-ended questions prompt the discussion on communication styles, work preferences, and multigenerational collaboration challenges and opportunities. Active listening and follow-up prompts encouraged detailed responses and deeper exploration of themes.

Data Analysis

The audio-recorded interviews are transcribed verbatim following Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006) reflexive thematic analysis. Transcription ensures the capture of every detail and nuance expressed by participants during the interview. This verbatim data is then carefully reviewed and coded to identify recurring themes and patterns related to collaboration across generations. This process involved moving between the data and emerging themes to capture the essence of participant's lived experiences with Multigenerational collaboration, as emphasized by Moustakas (1994).

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations in the study involve obtaining informed consent, ensuring confidentiality, and respecting participants boundaries. Participants are given the option to withdraw at any time, upholding their well-being and rights while conducting the study.

Informed Consent must be provided with a clear and comprehensive explanation of the research study before they are asked to participate. This explanation, often called an informed consent document, should detail the study's purpose, the procedures involved, any potential risks or discomforts that participants may experience, and the anticipated benefits of participation.

Confidentiality and Privacy is most important in any research study. This means keeping all participant identities and personal data confidential. Whenever possible, data should be anonymized to further safeguard participant privacy. Right to Withdraw must be clear that participants have the right to withdraw from the study at any time, and for any reason, without penalty. This right should be clearly explained in the informed consent document and reiterated throughout the research process. Participants should also be assured that their decision to withdraw does not affect their relationship with the researcher or any institution involved in the study.

Results and Discussion

This section dives into the study's core findings, presenting the data and its analysis with transparency. Researchers begin by outlining the methods used for data collection and analysis. Next, researchers provide a detailed profile of the research participants, offering a clear picture of the sample population. Following this, the chapter delves into the key results, with dedicated sections for discussing

and presenting the findings. Finally, researchers conclude with a concise summary, solidifying the chapter's crucial takeaways.

The section details the research methods used to gather data from five participants. This data was then analyzed using Moustakas (1994) approach to answer the research questions. This section focuses on the data collection process. Interviews with five participants, chosen through purposive sampling, were conducted in March 2024. Data saturation was achieved after interviewing all five participants, indicating the information gathered was sufficient. Most of the data used in the analysis stemmed from the interviews.

Operational Data Collection

The researchers interviewed five (5) participants who were chosen through purposive sampling to ensure their lived experiences aligned with the research questions four (4) participants are interviewed face-to-face while one (1) participant is interviewed online. After receiving and signing an informed consent form, the researchers conducted interviews using Moustakas (1994) guide to gather data relevant to the study's objectives as well as to record their verbatim.

Operational Data Analysis

This study adopted a qualitative approach rooted in hermeneutic phenomenology. Inspired by Moustakas (1994), the research focused on understanding participants' lived experiences within a particular context, emphasizing their subjective perspectives. To gain deeper insight into these experiences, the analysis adhered to Moustakas (1994) structure.

To understand how participants experienced working in Multigenerational settings, researchers analyzed their responses. They identified recurring patterns within the data, grouping them into categories that eventually formed central themes. This process allowed them to condense the most significant aspects of the information. Additionally, the researchers considered universal structure for data analysis, which included key elements of: time, space, relationship to self and others, bodily concerns, casual or intentional structures, and essence.

Theme 1: Perception of stereotypes

Category 1: Observation of generational stereotypes

Some of the codes gathered are Differences in Expectations, Values, Technological Proficiency, Adaptability, Attitudes. Employees across different generations have acknowledged the existence of stereotypes tied to their age groups. There's a common belief that younger generations possess superior tech skills and are more proficient in navigating online tasks, contrasting with the perceived struggle of older generations to adapt to rapidly evolving digital platforms.

In the interview that was conducted one participant answered, "Before, when I was in my prime, I've always thought that I am productive. I can do all things that will be given to me. Strike anywhere. That was me before when I was younger. But when the time came I became 50 years old. This time I felt that my generation could not keep up with the generation of new pictures today. Of course, more techie, right? And they know more when it comes to online activities, online projects." (see Martha Line #8).

Martha's response highlights the challenge of older individuals feeling increasingly disconnected from technological advancements as they age. This widening gap in technological proficiency between generations emphasizes the necessity for targeted efforts to bridge this disparity and ensure equitable access to digital resources.

"So maybe the stereotypes were when it comes uhh when umm how would we understand their behavior. Like for example, how would they respond when someone younger than them taught them." (see Houston Line #3).

Houston's observation reveals a common perception that younger individuals may exhibit less respect to authority figures. This suggests potential friction between generations, emphasizing the need to confront and mitigate these stereotypes for improved Multigenerational communication.

"As for the older, it's also difficult to understand because what.. in... they are the ones they like more, they are the ones who follow. In... Especially in the example there are rules and regulations on what. They always seem to fight for what they want. When you're older... that's how it is when you're older, you just feel respect. Whatever they want, that's all." (see Rosie Line #6).

Rosie's perspective emphasizes the difficulty in understanding and engaging with older generations, particularly concerning their autonomy and resistance to external authority. This emphasizes the importance of employing patience and empathy when navigating interactions with older individuals, recognizing and respecting their preferences and viewpoints.

Category 2: Personal experiences with stereotypes

Some of the codes gathered are Resistance to Technological Changes, Perceptions of Career Stability, Challenges in Adapting to Online Platforms, Interactions with Younger Generations, Emotional Responses.

Personal experiences show the impact of these stereotypes on individual employees. Some older employees may find themselves struggling with the pace of technological change, leading to feelings of frustration and inadequacy as they struggle to transition from familiar, paper-based methods to digital workflows. Younger employees may face assumptions that underestimate their commitment

to long-term career paths, with assumptions that they are more prone to job-hopping and lack the dedication to stability. These individual struggles highlight the complexity and nuance of generational dynamics in the workplace.

In the interview that was conducted one participant answered, “because I'm used to what, doing my jobs only through written works. I don't use computers. Class records, written. Lesson plan, written. Even if I close my eyes, I can do it. Even if I don't have a book in hand, I can do it. Now, you need to open the link, open the data, encode it in Google. Oh my, I can't do that which is common now a days which is what the new generations love because they can adapt more. That's it, that's my hardship, that's my struggle because I can't do my papers, my jobs using the online platform.”(see Martha Line #10).

Martha's narrative highlights the struggle of adapting to technological advancements, particularly in the transition from traditional paper-based work to online platforms. Her reliance on n written works underscores a generational gap in digital literacy, as she expresses difficulty in navigating tasks that younger generations find intuitive. This struggle reflects much wide challenges faced by older individuals in keeping pace with technological evolution and adapting to new modes of work and communication.

“If uhh is younger, they think that uhh seems to want to do more in life, so they are thinking that the younger ones are the ones who will stay shorter than the older ones. Because the older ones seem to think that umm they want.. they want for as like kind of settlement or stable job, but for the younger generations at their younger age they think that umm those ages just using the company for them to step up and acquires skills that they need for the better job that they want to have.” (see Houston Line #4).

Houston's observation delves into the perception of longevity in the workplace across generations. Younger individuals are seen as more transient, seeking varied experiences and skill acquisition before moving on to better opportunities. In contrast, older generations are perceived as prioritizing stability and long-term employment. This disparity in career outlooks emphasize differences in values and priorities between generations, potentially leading to misunderstandings or misalignment in professional settings.

“When the pandemic came way back 2000 is 2020, we had online classes, we had online meetings and it was very hard for me. Very hard for me doing things because I don't know anything about computers. I still need to adapt myself and I still need to ask my daughters and even my nieces and nephews to help me out do my things and when it comes to... When entering face to face, I had more difficulty because the younger ones in the me, they must be millennials because they are in their 20s, right? They are the ones that are easier to catch. That's where I had a hard time when it came to work. I have...Sometimes I have self-pity, I have anxiety because I cannot work, I cannot do things. I still need to ask my friend to do things for me. Younger than me, younger so he can learn more easily.” (see Martha Line #8).

Martha further emphasizes the profound impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on individuals' technological adaptation and mental well-being. The sudden shift to online platforms for work and education posed significant challenges for those lacking digital literacy, exacerbating feelings of isolation and inadequacy. The reliance on younger family members for assistance underscores the multigenerational dynamics at play, with younger generations often serving as guides and mentors in navigating technological landscapes.

However, amidst these stereotypes, there are instances where collaboration transcends generational barriers. Employees recognize the inherent value in blending the seasoned experience of older generations with the fresh perspectives and innovative ideas brought by their younger counterparts

This Multigenerational exchange fosters a rich culture of learning, support, and mutual respect, where diverse viewpoints converge to drive innovation and problem-solving. Additionally, there's a growing acknowledgment of the educational disparities between generations, with older employees embracing opportunities to learn from the technical prowess of younger colleagues, thus fostering a relationship that enhances overall workplace dynamics.

There's a notable shift in work attitudes among individuals belonging to Generation Z, when compared to preceding generations. Gen Z exhibits a distinct approach to work, displaying desire towards shorter job tenures and a diminished capacity for enduring challenges within a particular role. This trend suggests a tendency towards job-hopping or seeking immediate gratification over committing to long career paths like the older generation, leaning away from the traditional values or loyalty and dedication to a profession.

“because today's GenZs have a different attitude towards... their attitude towards work is different. But we also noticed that when the GenZ were with us at work, they didn't wait for someone who didn't have anything... At work, because most of us GenZs, when they get tired of work, resign immediately. Because they seem to feel about themselves umm..I can get more and better work what..ground because that is what is being done. Because we, the generation, are like, this is our job, we will love our job. The attitude of GenZ is easy to get bored.” (see Rosie Line #33).

Participants felt that Gen Z or Generation Z may exhibit lower levels of tolerance for dissatisfaction in their work environment. When faced fith challenges they are more inclined to resign and seek alternative employment, by the belief of they can easily find better prospects elsewhere. Which differ with the older generations, who prioritize stability and commitment to their current roles, viewing their jobs as valuable and worthy of appreciation.

“I think it contributes because uhm the new generation is better, what are they better, their learning uhh is upgrading. So it's like

we...The old people in the company, we need the ideas of the new generation more. Because things are changing, the system, so the new generations are more upgraded, more updated in terms of our old workers.” (see Sheila Line #12).

Participants highlight the continuous learning and skill upgrading characteristic of the new generation, suggesting that their innovative ideas play a vital role in keeping the company's practices current and relevant. Sheila implies that older employees, labeled as the "old," stand to benefit from the fresh perspectives and technological savvy of their younger counterparts. This underscores the importance of integrating the knowledge and innovation brought by younger employees to navigate evolving systems and maintain competitiveness.

“At the level, when you are the age of 50, they can no longer relate to new technologies. Isn't that what adults learn? Compared to you millennials. Those of your generation, what about technology, you are faster... call it. It is easier for us to understand the technology compared to the oldies.” (see Sheila Line #23).

Sheila emphasizes the struggle of older generations to adapt to new technologies, pointing to a significant generation gap in digital literacy and comfort with digital tools. In contrast, millennials, as digital natives, demonstrate greater ease and fluency in utilizing technology, benefiting from their upbringing in a technology-rich environment.

“Actually, there are no differences because it's our company. So, when the GenZs joined us, although it was boring to be teenagers lifetimes in the generation, what happened.. our group was happy because today's GenZs, they have a different attitude towards... their attitude towards work is different. But we also noticed that when the GenZ were with us at work, they didn't wait for someone who didn't have anything... At work, because most of us GenZs, when they get tired of work, resign immediately. Because they seem to feel about themselves umm..I can get more and better work what..ground because that is what is being done. Because we, the generation, are like, this is our job, we will love our job. The attitude of GenZ is easy to get bored.”(see Rosie Line #33).

Rosie's reflection provides key insights into how the introduction of Generation Z employees has influenced work attitudes within the company, particularly in contrast to older generations like hers. She notes a noticeable shift in GenZ's approach to work, characterized by a shorter tolerance for dissatisfaction and a quicker inclination to resign. This observation highlights a potential divide in work ethic and values between generations, which could impact workplace cohesion and productivity.

“Because now here oh,. The... All the children in... were on one side tok-tok-tok-tok.. Cell phone, cell phone. My grandchildren. Pure, It's all (inaudible). You know it can be used for everything. But I hope you can use it at work, in... to be useful to yourselves. But don't, don't gossip.” (see Chester Line #34).

Chester's statement offers insights into the prevalence of technology, particularly cell phones, among younger individuals, as exemplified by his grandchildren. He observes that cellphones are a constant presence in their lives, indicating their widespread use for various purposes. Chester highlights the potential of these devices to be utilized for productivity and personal development, urging younger individuals to harness them effectively in the workplace. However, he also cautions against engaging in gossip or idle chatter, suggesting a concern about the potential distractions posed by excessive use of technology.

Theme 2: Impact of stereotypes on collaboration

Category 3: Stereotypes in action

Some of the codes gathered are Recognition of Experience vs. Fresh Perspectives in Collaboration, Multigenerational Learning and Support, Educational Differences and Support in the Workplace. Despite the existence of stereotypes, there are instances where collaboration transcends generational differences. Employees recognize the value of blending experience with fresh perspectives in the workplace. Older employees, drawing from their wealth of experience, understand the significance of remaining open to new ideas and suggestions from younger colleagues. This multigenerational exchange fosters a culture of learning and support, where both seasoned professionals and newcomers contribute to innovation and problem-solving.

In the interview that was conducted one participant answered, “some time there are also moments when it is heard that they have experience by their age so sometimes there are people who apply who have a lot of experience of work and then only that time they apply to try a kind of job that is out of their comfort zone so it seems like they think that most of the time the tenure partner is the one who can explore the idea but they are also opening the opportunity for in the floor for the new partners or new employees who can provide perspective and suggestion.” (see Houston Line #5).

Houston's observation highlights the mutual benefit derived from Multigenerational collaboration. Older employees, often characterized by their extensive work experience, may occasionally step out of their comfort zones to explore new roles or ideas. This openness creates opportunities for newer employees to contribute fresh perspectives and suggestions, fostering a culture of innovation and continuous improvement. The exchange of ideas between generations not only enriches the work environment but also promotes a sense of inclusivity and mutual respect among employees.

“They even help us more. Because in the generation if you notice the educational what is it? although we also graduated, but studying now is really different. We study especially on the computer. We understand the computer but GenZ is better now, So that's what helps us.” (see Rose Line #8).

Rose's perspective further emphasizes the relationship between generations in knowledge transfer. While acknowledging the differences in educational backgrounds, particularly regarding technology proficiency, Rose highlights the willingness of younger employees, often classified as Generation Z, to assist older colleagues. Despite having received different types of education, older employees recognize the technological expertise of younger generations and actively seek their guidance and support. This collaborative approach facilitates skill sharing and enhances overall productivity in the workplace.

“because there is no one upstairs who is old. He has experience in business. He has no experience in business but is good at technology. Having said this, what we want to do, the children have many ideas. Using technology, sir, this is how we will do it. We will do this and say this, or accept it as long as it is done well, feedback is good feedback, good, go ahead or improve it, improve so technology based because we are not children, but in our experience we will look into it if you have a suggestion it's okay not but if it's okay, it's approved. As for me, I'll wait for feedback, did it get better? Is the effect ugly? Etc. Okay, so, depending on the feedback, I will decide again. Okay. It doesn't seem like much, let's improve? Okay, we can change it. Okay, let's swap and improve. The amount depends. When feedback is given, the decision will be made.” (see Chester Line #52).

Chester's perspective provides insights on the decision-making dynamics within the organization, particularly the interaction between experienced individuals and those adept in technology. He describes a collaborative process where individuals with business acumen provide insights, while those proficient in technology offer innovative ideas. This collaborative exchange enables a thorough evaluation of proposed initiatives, considering both practicality and technological feasibility.

Theme 3: Generational differences in communication styles

Category 1: Challenges and misunderstandings

Some of the codes gathered are Linguistic Barriers, Adaptation in Communication, Preference for Interaction Within the Same Generation, Emotional Impact of Communication Challenges. Employees from different generations have expressed generational differences in communication styles such as challenges and misunderstanding in communication, particularly concerning linguistic differences and adaptation.

There's a struggle to understand the language and vocabulary used by younger generations, such as Gen Z. This difficulty is exemplified by unfamiliar words or phrases like "Omsim," which can leave older generations feeling perplexed and disconnected. One participant shared their experience, stating, “Because in GenZ, we can't adapt to their words, especially the words they use, we don't understand. We can't adapt to those... because many of our GenZ are employed. So what they speak, we can't... We can't understand because the words they have are the ones they turn around like, Omsim, we can't. We will ask, what does that mean?.” (see Rosie Line #3).

Rosie's statement highlights the challenge faced by older generations in understanding and adapting to the communication styles of younger generations, particularly Gen Z. She specifically mentions difficulties in comprehending the vocabulary and linguistic nuances used by younger individuals, such as words being flipped or unfamiliar slang like "Omsim." This highlights a significant gap in communication between generations, emphasizing the need for efforts to bridge this divide and promote effective multigenerational communication in the workplace.

Moreover, Rosie really finds it difficult to communicate or understand Generation Z. Rosie also stated that ““With Millennials, that's what we're more like, more...that's where we focus, especially on friendship, that's where we're based. Ahh Although we talk to the GenZs, it's hard to understand their attitude. That's it. So we were there in the generation where we were more than there, we wanted to be with them more.” (see Rosie line #5).

She notes that while she and her peers, who are Millennials, primarily focus on building friendships and relationships within their own age group, they do interact with Gen Z individuals. However, Rosie finds it difficult to comprehend the attitudes and behaviors of the Gen Z generation. This suggests a potential challenge in Bridging the Generation Gap between Millennials and Gen Z in terms of communication styles, values, and preferences. Rosie's struggle to understand the attitudes of Gen Z individuals may hinder effective communication and relationship-building across generations in the workplace. Therefore, addressing this challenge requires efforts to foster mutual understanding and empathy between Millennials and Gen Z, enabling more harmonious interactions and collaborations within the organization.

“I experienced that with my co-teachers because of course they are new and younger. They are younger than me now. So, it seems like it's hard to make... What's it called? It's hard to make a deal. Especially when it comes to... Various problems and also having... A bit older age. We also attack problems differently, especially when it comes to work. It's like you feel like you're left behind, like you feel like you don't belong. That, I experienced that. I really had anxiety with that. That's why? It's like the difficulty of idealizing, the difficulty of communicating with... I'm not your age when it comes to work. I feel like I want to retire early. “ (See Martha Line #15).

Martha's reflection sheds light on the challenges she faces when working alongside younger colleagues, particularly in navigating differences in age and experience. She expresses difficulty in dealing with various issues, especially as she perceives herself as older than her co-teachers. Martha describes feeling left behind and experiencing a sense of not belonging, which has led to feelings of anxiety and a desire to retire early. This emphasizes the emotional toll that generational differences in the workplace can have on individuals, impacting their sense of belonging, confidence, and overall well-being. Martha's experience reflects the importance of

fostering inclusion, understanding, and support across generations to create a work environment where all employees feel valued and respected, regardless of age or experience. Addressing these challenges requires proactive efforts to promote Multigenerational collaboration, communication, and mutual respect within the organization.

However, Martha tried adapting a communication approach, particularly when interacting with younger colleagues in the workplace. "I also apply that to work, especially childhood. I change the conversation, the attack of dialogue. Right? When the dialogue is your age, it's like, oh, this is how we are, our activities before. And then you choose the language. But when the person in front of you is quite young, oh, Beshi! Or isn't it? You adapt with their generation. You also try to do things that you adapt the innovations you see in them. That's how you can enter their world." (see Martha Line #11).

She believes that changing her communication style and dialogue approach based on the age group she is engaging with comes for much better understanding and communication results between communication with older and younger generations. By using terms like "Beshi" and adjusting her communication approach to align with the younger generation's norms and language, Martha demonstrates a willingness to adapt and connect with her younger colleagues. This adaptability fosters better understanding and relationship across generational divides in the workplace, ultimately contributing to more effective communication and collaboration.

"Because it's different when you approach your age, you're the same age and it's different when you approach another age or another generation. It's more like, uhm how would I be able to start a conversation or build a relationship with them that would somehow give an impact on my perspective as well and with respect to them." (see Houston Line #8)."

Houston's statement underscores the nuanced approach required when initiating conversations or building relationships with individuals from different age groups or generations in the workplace. She highlights the distinction between interacting with peers of the same age and engaging with those from different generations. Her challenge lies in determining how to start conversations and develop relationships that not only impact her perspective but also respect the perspectives of others. Houston struggled with understanding the nuances of communication styles, preferences, and cultural differences across generations, which could hinder his ability to establish meaningful connections with individuals from diverse age groups. This suggests an awareness of the need for empathy, understanding, and mutual respect when bridging generational gaps in communication and relationship-building within the workplace. By acknowledging these differences and striving to create meaningful connections, Houston aims to foster a collaborative and inclusive work environment that values diverse perspectives and experiences.

Theme 4: Impact of technology on multigenerational collaboration

Category 2: Technology proficiency

Some of the codes gathered are Resourcefulness in Communication Strategies, Need for Understanding and Studying Generations for Effective Communication, Importance of Acceptance of Generational Differences in Communication.

Participants emphasized the importance of being resourceful in communication strategies to effectively engage with individuals across different generations. They recognized the need to understand and study generational characteristics to enhance communication. Moreover, acceptance of generational differences was highlighted as crucial for fostering effective interactions.

In Martha's interview, she reflected on these challenges, stating, "So, we should be resourceful on thinking on what innovations we are going to do by trying to communicate and by trying to deal with people with the different generations so that we can keep up with that and this is why I am having a struggle but then maybe it's for me to step up so I can also use the strategy of what do I need to study, study the generation, study the things that you have to learn. Acceptance is also important. Acceptance of what generation you are into and what generation you are trying to deal with." (See Martha Line #12)

Martha's insight underscores the necessity for adaptable communication strategies that acknowledge and accommodate generational differences, ultimately facilitating more effective multigenerational communication.

Moreover, Sheila highlighted the benefits of interacting with individuals from different generations, emphasizing the value of their fresh perspectives and up-to-date knowledge.

She noted that younger generations often bring new ideas informed by the latest trends and advancements, particularly in education and technology. Sheila emphasized the importance of this updated knowledge in both academic and professional settings, where newer generations tend to be more adaptive at navigating modern systems and technologies.

In her interview, Sheila stated, "I prefer the different generation because uhh... you get new ideas. They can share with you the most updated lessons they learn at school. Because the one we used to study, maybe that's what it is. If it used to be Microsoft, now there are many more updated systems. So it's easier for them to... They understand easily. More in schooling, more updated. It's like that at work too. So, the new generations are more updated in the systems." (See Sheila Line #15)

Sheila's perspective underscores the potential for multigenerational collaboration to foster innovation and facilitate knowledge sharing, particularly in domains heavily influenced by technological advancements. This highlights the importance of leveraging generational diversity to enhance communication and drive progress in various contexts.

Theme 5: Impact on individuals and organization

Category 1: Experiences with Multigenerational collaboration

Some of the codes gathered are Success of Multigenerational Projects, Comfort Zone and Innovation, Adaptation to Change, Embracing Diversity in Collaboration.

“It was good and it was a better idea that our principal used the different age brackets. Because the project that is being done will be more successful when the ages are different together. Because when you're both older together, it's like they're wearing something, boxed. right? But when there are new ones, you will come out of your box, eh. You will come out of your comfort zone. You will realize, ah, why not try the other, why not try the ideas of the younger generation? Okay, let's see. If it is effective, let's adopt it. It's like that. So there are actually better results.” (see Martha Line #22)

Martha praises their principal for involving individuals from different groups in a project, believing that success is more likely when diverse age brackets collaborate. They note that working with people of varying ages helps individuals step out of their comfort zones and consider new ideas, particularly those from younger generations. This approach encourages openness to innovation and a willingness to try new approaches. Overall, Martha's perspective underscores the importance of embracing diversity in collaboration, particularly in terms of age differences, as it can lead to innovative ideas and better project outcomes.

“Maybe you really just have to deal with it. Because we cannot change things. There's nothing permanent. We thought that what we are used to, that will be your work all throughout. But...If there is something constant, that is the change. That we have to embrace, we have to accept, and we have to live with it. Because changes give us better results, gives us better understanding, especially when dealing with different people..” (see Martha Line #25)

Martha emphasizes the inevitability of change and the need to accept and embrace it, noting that change provides better results and understanding, especially in dealing with different people. Martha highlights the importance of adaptation to change in multigenerational collaborations, where embracing can lead to positive outcomes.

“Ahm These programs were created by the Department of Education. Maybe they are the ones who thought about how the older generation can cope up with the new generation in the program they want to impose like what's new now. You read and you teach you only have and you only concentrate into one objective. But now because the idea of different generations has been introduced. Even in the department itself, there are different ideas because sometimes children are in charge. Children sometimes become the heads of the Department of Education. So there's a new attack, there's a new technique called like what's the name of collaborating, integration.” (see Martha Line #24).

Martha highlights how the Department of Education has adapted to changing times by creating programs that cater to both older and younger generations and also mention the inclusion of ideas from different age groups, leading to diverse perspectives within the Department and the development of innovative approaches. This adaption is evident in the inclusion of younger leaders who bring new techniques like collaboration and integration. Overall, Martha emphasizes the importance of adapting to change by incorporating ideas from different generations, which has led to innovative programs within the Department of Education.

“ Yes. Actually, the different generation is really a big help because they can share each idea of something... of a team. Even if the attitude is different, of course when it comes to work, you have to pursue the right thing. So we also listen to GenZ because... ayy ah of course more... although they are missing from... their personality that we are looking for because we are generation (Y). But that's more successful because we get different, different ideas and knowledge.” (see Rosie Line #26)

Rosie highlights the success of Multigenerational collaboration in a team, noting the valuable contribution of different generations in sharing diverse ideas and knowledge. And also emphasizes the importance of pursuing common goals despite differences in personality and work approaches. The speaker also acknowledged the significance of listening to Gen Z team members for their fresh perspectives, contributing to the success of projects. Overall, the speaker's perspective underscores the effectiveness of integrating diverse generational perspectives for project success.

“Very timing, what? Your topic. There was something... There was a wider understanding of what they implemented and it was possible. You can use what you used to before and then inject the new build of new generations to attack or implement it in your working place. That's it. Then you just have to study it and you just have to go with learning the process. You need to study the process. You need that acceptance to be able to change and adapt the change to yourself.”(See Martha line #26)

In Martha's perspective highlighting a recent broadening of understanding that has emerged regarding new implementations. Also suggest blending familiar practices with innovative ideas from younger generations, reflecting an adaptive mindset and emphasizing the importance of studying and understanding the change process, highlighting the need to accept change for personal growth and adaptation. The mention of injecting new ideas from younger generations established practices also implies a collaborative and cooperative approach across generations, aligning with experiences in multigenerational collaboration.

“ They even help us more. Because in the generation if you notice the educational what is it? although we also graduated, but studying now is really different. We study especially on the computer. We understand the computer but GenZ is better now, So that's what helps

us.” (See Rosie Line #8)

Rosie’s perspective highlights the importance of adapting to change in a multigenerational and mentioned how younger generations, particularly Gen Z, excel in computer skills compared to their generation. This recognition reflects an ongoing need to adapt to new technologies. Rosie’s also emphasizes the value of multigenerational learning, where older individuals benefit from the expertise of younger generations.

Conclusions

This research explored how employees from different generations perceive collaboration in the workplace and while the generational stereotypes exist, the participants have acknowledged their limitations and recognized the value of having a Multigenerational workforce in a collaborative setup.

Generational stereotypes

Employees have identified the stereotypes around technology usage be it in work or in their personal lives, the work ethic and career commitment across generations. However, they also saw the potential for collaboration and learning from each other’s strengths.

Collaboration challenges

Linguistic barriers, different communication styles, and emotional responses were highlighted by the employees as hurdles to effective and efficient communication. The study emphasizes the need for empathy, adaptability, and understanding to bridge these gaps.

Successful collaboration

Participants reported positive experiences from working together with diverse teams. Integrating innovative and new ideas, embracing the change, and maximizing the expertise of each generation can lead to innovation, knowledge sharing, and ultimately, organizational success.

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